

IMPLEMENTATION OF HYDROGEN ENERGY AND RESOLVING THE KEY PROBLEMS

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Abstract: The paper includes a brief discussion on 'HYDROGEN ENERGY' as a resource for our future generation. It can be implemented despite having certain challenges. The main source of hydrogen energy is from fossil fuels, more specifically natural gas. Hydrogen energy can be used for work which needs high energy efficiency alongside overwhelming environmental and social benefits as well as economical support. Hydrogen energy is also used in large quantities in aeronautical and aviation sector. As fossil-fuels are limited and will soon face extinction, hence scientists and researchers from all over the world are trying their best to find a substitute for energy production as soon as possible. Solar panels, wind mills, hydro energy are also substitutes of degrading energy sources. However, it is not sufficient for the growing population. Hydrogen, being easily available, has the potential to sustainably meet the growing global energy requirements. Nevertheless, alongside numerous advantages of using hydrogen energy and hydrogen fuel cells, there are also various limitations which can sometimes prove to be extremely fatal.

Keywords: Hydrogen energy; High energy efficiency; Hydrogen fuel cell

1. INTRODUCTION

Hydrogen and energy share a long history together, from powering the first internal combustion engines over 200 years ago to becoming an integral part of the modern refining industry.

Hydrogen is a clean alternative for methane and other extremely toxic gases, also termed as natural gas. Hydrogen in its molecular form is easily found on earth in various forms, including water, glaciers, plants and even humans. However it is very scarce as gas. Hydrogen energy can be generated in a large number of resources including solar power, wind energy, hydro energy as well as natural gas, biogas.

A fuel is a chemical which releases energy on burning. When hydrogen is burnt with oxygen to release energy, it is termed as hydrogen fuel. As hydrogen in its gaseous state does not occur naturally in a large quantity on earth, it requires some other inputs. Hydrogen fuel can be produced by electrolysis of water or from methane. At present, hydrogen is produced from fossil fuels by steam reforming.

Production of hydrogen is classified in the terms of color. This includes:

- A) **Grey Hydrogen**— It is produced from the steam reforming of methane with the release of carbon dioxide as a by-product.
- B) **Blue Hydrogen**— It is produced from natural gases with carbon dioxide as a by-product.
- C) **Green Hydrogen**— It is obtained by electrolysis when electricity is run through water to separate the hydrogen.

Today the preliminary uses of hydrogen are in petroleum refining and ammonia production. Researches show that transportation is the main market that will use hydrogen as an alternative of petrol and diesel. It is also found that hydrogen fuels will soon replace the aviation industry as well as the aerospace industry. Likewise, Space X has also been using hydrogen for rocket propulsions and take-offs.

We know combustion of methane releases a large amount of carbon dioxide as side product in the atmosphere, which creates an impact on climate. When replaced with hydrogen, there is no production of carbon dioxide. Hence, in recent years hydrogen is considered as a great substitute for natural gas. According to the current reports, use of hydrogen fuels has been found to be helpful to reduce the concern of global warming. Not until May 2022, researchers have come to a drastic conclusion stating that use of hydrogen also has a huge impact on climate change. Excess use of hydrogen fuels eventually leads to the increase of other greenhouse gases such as methane, ozone, and water vapor resulting in indirect warming.

2. IMPLEMENTATION OF HYDROGEN ENERGY

Hydrogen energy has been implemented in multiple fields in different ways.

Some uses of hydrogen energy are as follows:

- **Producing Electricity:** Hydrogen fuel cells are made by combining hydrogen and oxygen atoms. Hydrogen reacts with oxygen across an electrochemical cell to produce electricity. These hydrogen fuel cells can be used to supply electricity, power laptops or smart phones according to the size of the cell.
- **Use in Vehicles:** Hydrogen can be considered as an alternative vehicle fuel in India. It will be a more effective way to reduce the production of CFCs. In this way, we can reduce the use of harmful radiation emitting fuels. Also, hydrogen fuel cells are more effective for the nature.
- **Liquid hydrogen as rocket fuel:** When liquid hydrogen is burned with liquid oxygen, it has a low molecular weight and high energy output. The main engine of the space shuttle uses liquid hydrogen as a fuel as it can produce the huge up thrust which is required for the launching of rocket.
- **Backup of power:** At the preliminary stage the hydrogen fuel cells can be used to store energy as a backup. It can be used in the hospitals, laboratories and other workplaces where electricity is needed at a high amount.
- **Usage in Mobiles:** The hydrogen fuel cells can be used in mobiles for power generation. Amount of power needed in a mobile is much lesser than in any other sector. Also, hydrogen fuel cells can be charged easily. Thus, it is also portable.

- **Use in household devices:** Hydrogen can be used for power supply in the small household appliances. For example, torch, radio, television etc. If this process succeeds then later on hydrogen can be used for the main supply of the house.
- **Use in Submarines:** Some military submarines like the German Type 212 uses hydrogen fuel cells as an alternative of nuclear power with long range and silent cruising.

USE OF HYDROGEN FUEL CELLS IN AEROSPACE INDUSTRY

Hydrogen fuel cells have been gaining attention as a viable alternative to traditional fossil fuels in the aerospace industry. The aerospace industry is a major consumer of fossil fuels, and the shift towards hydrogen fuel cells has the potential to reduce carbon emissions and increase the sustainability of air travel.

Powering aircraft: Hydrogen fuel cells can be used to power aircrafts. Thus, it provides an alternative to traditional jet fuel. Fuel cells offer several benefits over traditional jet fuel, such as reduced emissions and noise pollution. In addition, fuel cells can provide a reliable and efficient source of power, improving the safety and performance of aircraft.

Auxiliary power units: Hydrogen fuel cells can also be used as auxiliary power units (APUs) in aircraft. APUs provides power to aircraft systems such as air conditioning and lighting while the aircraft is on the ground.

3. ADVANTAGES OF USING HYDROGEN ENERGY

The use of hydrogen has proven to be highly advantageous in a number of ways:

- Hydrogen energy is **renewable and readily available**.
- Hydrogen is a **clean and flexible energy** source to support zero carbon emission strategies
- **It is most powerful and energy efficient than fossil fuels:** Hydrogen fuel cell technology provides a high-density source of energy with good energy efficiency. Hydrogen has the highest energy content of any common fuel by weight.
- **No noise or visual pollution:** Unlike other renewable sources of energy, hydrogen does not create noise or emit smoke or cause any other kind of visual pollution.
- **Long time usage:** Hydrogen fuel cells are not significantly impacted due to climate change or cold weather, unlike EVs (electric vehicles). These advantages are maximized when coupled with short charging times.
- **Ideal for use in remote areas:** Hydrogen based energy can be used via local circulation instead of diesel or coal based power and heating.
- **Versatile:** With the advancement of technology, hydrogen fuel cells are able to provide energy for a variety of stationary and mobile applications. Similar to the ICE power plants, the fuel tanks and engine size are decoupled, in contrast to battery based power, hence providing great flexibility in design.
- **Democratization of power supply:** Since hydrogen fuel cells have the potential to reduce dependency on fossil fuels, it can help in huge democratization of power supply in different forms. Especially in areas where dependency on fossil fuels is highest, hydrogen fuel cells prove to be of great help.

4. KEY CHALLENGES OF HYDROGEN ENERGY

- **Hydrogen storage and delivery:** Hydrogen is very light weight. As a result, it is compressed at high pressure and low temperature of -253°C . These steps require extra energy investment, thus efficiency drops. Transportation of hydrogen energy is far more complex than other fossil fuels.
- **Safe handling of hydrogen energy:** Hydrogen is a highly flammable gas. Hydrogen burns in air at concentrations ranging from 4 to 75%. Therefore, strict regulations must be followed to ensure safety and avoid any fatality.
- **Limited availability of fueling stations and charging points:** In California, hydrogen energy is already being used in the vehicles. But the high cost of fuels and limited availability of hydrogen fueling stations has been a huge challenge. So, the production of hydrogen fueled vehicles is also limited.
- **Cost of raw materials:** Metals including platinum and iridium are typically required as catalysts in hydrogen fuel cells. Few special types of electrolyzes are also needed. This makes it cost ineffective. As a result, large usage is not feasible at the earliest.

5. SOLUTIONS TO THE PROBLEMS :

- Researchers are continuing their research on new cathode catalysts to be used in hydrogen fuel cells. A more abundant element may be discovered which is suitable for the job, thus making it more cost effective.
- In the hydrogen fuel cells, another segment may be connected. This new segment could serve the purpose of absorbing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere (using the carbon capture and utilization procedure (CCU)) and actively release hydrogen with the use of water. This released hydrogen will again be used as fuel. This continuous process shall also help in reducing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere and also maintain water level. On the other hand, hydrogen fuel cells can also be operated in a continuous manner in a cycle.
- More charging points should be installed on roadsides, thereby enabling a growth in hydrogen energy powered vehicles. This will also help reduce the dependency on petrol and diesel.
- **Chemical storage:** Hydrogen can also be stored in chemical compounds, such as ammonia or methanol. These compounds can be easier to transport and store than hydrogen gas.

6. CONCLUSION

The paper briefly points out the present condition of hydrogen energy, the pros and cons of using it, and tries to give a solution which can be implemented in near future.

The importance of this report is to embrace the advancement of technology and adopt the use of hydrogen fuel cells in day-to-day life.

Since fossil fuels such as coal, petroleum, and crude oil and so on, are on the verge of disappearance, we must adapt to newer processes energy production.

Hydrogen fuel cells have the capability of replacing fossil fuels although it does have its limitations. Governments and industries worldwide have recognized the importance of hydrogen energy and are investing in its development and deployment. The successful implementation of hydrogen energy will require a coordinated effort from various stakeholders, including policymakers, investors, researchers and industry players. With collaborative efforts and continued progress, hydrogen energy can become a significant contributor to a sustainable and clean energy future.

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